

STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING BASED ON STRAIN DISTRIBUTIONS OF A COMPOSITE TRAIN CARBODY

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SUMMARY

The lightweight composite train carbody gives many advantages such as fuel reduction, reducing burden for railway systems, etc. In this study, global monitoring of composite carbody using strain data is suggested. From the acquired strain using FBG sensors, the deformation shapes can be estimated and warning will be shown in the emergency case.

Keywords: composite carbody, strain based SHM, FBG (Fiber Bragg Grating) sensors

INTRODUCTION

A structural weight reduction of trains offers many advantages such as increased fuel efficiency, increased operating speed, reduced burden for railway systems. Thus, these technologies for reducing weight have been applied to new lightweight trains [1]. Among these technologies, the application of composite materials is very promising due to higher specific strength and stiffness over other conventional materials [2]. For examples, there are Turbostar (UK), Puma (Germany), RARe-520 (Switzerland) as new lightweight trains adopting composite materials. In Korea, the Korea Railroad Research Institute (KRRRI) is also developing a composite train carbody for the Korean tilting train (TTX). This composite carbody adopted a hybrid design concept which consists of a composite sandwich bodyshell and stainless steel reinforcing frames [1,2].

However, enhancing the reliability of such composite structures is required to safely operate. To enhance reliability, structural health monitoring (SHM) may be applied in various kinds of composite structures [3-6]. A global strain monitoring is particularly useful for large structures such as aircraft and trains. To apply this technique, efficient sensor locations must be constructed over a large region. Ryu et al. [7] determined the appropriate FBG strain sensor locations for buckling monitoring of a composite wing box using FEA. Kiddy et al. [8] used FEM results to search large stress regions of a submarine for the optimal locations to attach FBG sensors. Kesavan et al. [9] also performed a FEA of complex composite structures to obtain strain distributions for efficiently detecting damages. Clearly, the FEA results of a composite carbody should be very useful for the determination of appropriate sensor locations.

To precisely determine the integrity of a carbody, the extent of any deformation must be estimated, because the threshold stresses and critical regions are different for each deformation loading case. Reconstruction methods using strain data have been suggested by various researchers to estimate deformations. Using the strain data from optical fiber sensors, Nishio et al. [10] and Kang et al. [11] reconstructed the deformation of 2-D plates and 1-D beams. However, their methods using the governing equations could not be applied to 3-D structures such as a carbody because of the large and complex computations that would be necessary. Thus, in this study, the method of least squares was used to determine the difference between the strains in the FEA results and the measured strains. In other words, the case in which the root mean square (RMS) value is a minimum was chosen to be the matched deformation case from the deformation loading database by means of FEA.

Finally, a health management program using an FEM/FBG hybrid method was developed. In this program, there is a post-processing algorithm for estimating the deformations, and the system provides a warning in case of dangerous situations. It was confirmed that this program showed adequate results after post-processing of various input strain distributions.

DETERMINATION OF SENSOR LOCATIONS

This study considers the relatively minor deformations that can occur due to various derailments and high speed operation on curved tracks because the application of conventional non-destructive evaluations (NDEs) to such deformations is not efficient.

Derailment situations can be categorized according to the number and the locations of derailed wheel sets. And high speed operation on a curved track is the highest deformation that occurs under normal operating conditions. In this situation, the maximum velocity is 180 km/hr and the radius of the curved track is 300 m with 150 mm cant.

Using the above deformation cases, finite element analyses were performed to determine the FBG sensor locations and the strain values for each loading case. The detailed FE analytical model (147,438 nodes and 143,800 elements) of the TTX includes a composite carbody, metal reinforcing frame, underframe and keystone-plates, etc. Fig. 1 shows the configurations of the composite TTX carbody model.

Figure 1. Configurations of detailed FE model of TTX composite carbody.

The boundary conditions (153 mm in the downward direction) for analyzing the derailment cases were given to the each wheel set as shown in Fig. 1. For analyzing the case of high speed operation on curved track, the accelerations (loading condition) of the carbody were calculated from the centripetal force and the gravity force. As analytical solver, ABAQUS/CAE was adopted.

Fig. 2 shows the strain distributions on deformed composite carbody of some representative FEA results. From these results, it was found that the characteristic strain regions for each case were positioned at the left and right bottom parts of the carbody. To check the characteristics of strain distributions, the strain data along these regions were extracted from the FEA results and were plotted in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Strain distributions on the deformed composite carbody for each case.

Figure 3. Plots of all strains along the bottom skirt of carbody.

Using the above strain plots, the FBG sensor locations were determined as shown in Fig. 3. The FBG sensor locations are the same as the high strain regions. At the bottom of each side of the carbody, one FBG sensor line with eight FBG sensors was used. Thus, there were two sensor lines with sixteen FBG sensors in total.

FEM/FBG HYBRID METHOD

For health management of composite carbody, the FEM/FBG hybrid method was devised. This method consists of finite element analyses to determine the sensor locations for each typical loading case and a post-processing algorithm to select the case that is the best match among the strain data acquired from the FBG sensors. In this study, however, there were no acquired sensor data from the tests of real carbody of TTX. Thus, the procedure of reproducing FBG sensor data was included for the simulation of measured data.

For the reproduced data closed to the real measured strains, the FEA strain results added with the random values could be used. Due to potential FBG sensor problems like misalignment of sensor axes, measurement noise, etc., there may be some variations from the exact measurement of the local strain (FEA results in this study). In order to add the random values (from -0.00005 to 0.00005) to the previous FEA results, the function of generating random values in the LabVIEW software was used. These strain values with their added variations are used as the simulated measurement inputs of a health management algorithm program.

In the next step, to determine the deformation case, the method of least squares was adopted, in which the sum of squared differences between the database strains and the

acquired strains has its least value. The following equation of RMS value was introduced for calculating the error between two strain data as a residual function.

$$R = \sqrt{(\varepsilon_{FEM,1} - \varepsilon_{FBG,1})^2 + (\varepsilon_{FEM,2} - \varepsilon_{FBG,2})^2 + \dots + (\varepsilon_{FEM,n} - \varepsilon_{FBG,n})^2} \quad (1)$$

If the reproduced data are entered as the acquired data, the RMS values are calculated at each data strain. Then, the case in which the RMS value is a minimum is chosen as the best fit to the deformation case selected from the database loading cases.

In the proposed system, when it is determined that deformation had occurred, the health of the carbody must be checked. To do this, the critical strains must be determined. The basic assumption in this step is that the stresses and strains are in linear relationships. From the EFA results and strength values (Table 1) of the carbody material, the limit stress values for each case were calculated. And the limit stress values had to be converted to the critical strains because FBG sensors are strain measured sensors. The resulting strain values for each deformation case are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Material properties of CF1263 carbon/epoxy.

Material properties	Values
Tensile elastic modulus in direction of warp, E_{wt} (GPa)	55.5
Tensile elastic modulus in direction of fill, E_{ft} (GPa)	48.3
Compressive elastic modulus in direction of warp, E_{wc} (GPa)	52.6
Compressive elastic modulus in direction of fill, E_{fc} (GPa)	52.1
Shear modulus, G_{12} (GPa)	3.81
Tensile strength in direction of warp, W_t (MPa)	936
Tensile strength in direction of fill, F_t (MPa)	885
Compressive strength in direction of warp, W_c (MPa)	542
Compressive strength in direction of fill, F_c (MPa)	513
Shear strength, S_{12} (MPa)	103
Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.099

Table 2 Determined critical strain values.

	Critical strain values
Case 1,2	0.005150
Case 3,4	0.005524
Case 5,6,7,8	0.01630104
Case 9,10	0.00461732
Case 11,12,13,14	0.005310
Case 15	0.009409

If the maximum strain of the acquired data is greater than the urgent strain value in the estimated deformation case, the post-processing program indicates an emergency. To enhance the efficiency of health management, searching the excessive stress region is required. In order to search for these regions, the boundary distance for FEA was calculated from the maximum strain values of the acquired data. From the FEA result using this boundary distance, the excessive stress regions can be determined (Fig. 4). This makes it possible to determine whether repair of the carbody is necessary. This is the strategy for determining the emergency state. Fig. 5 shows the overall procedures of FEM /FBG hybrid method. As a final step, the performance of this health management algorithm was verified. In this step, various cases with different strain levels and entirely shifted data were tested. To reproduce these various strain data, several FEAs were performed. The reproduced acquired data from the sensor locations were extracted from the FEA results.

Figure 4. High stress regions for emergency state.

Figure 5. Algorithm of the FEM/FBG hybrid method.

VERIFICATIONS

Fig. 6 shows the complete post-processing program using LabVIEW software with user friendly display. For verification of the post-processing program, various kinds of deformation cases such as derailment cases with different heights, some shifted strain cases and random strain cases were tested.

From these tests, if the RMS values were under 0.001, the program showed appropriate deformations with good agreements. Then, as shown in first figure in Fig. 6, the program offered the deformation case number, the plots of acquired strain data and derailment height. Moreover, if the maximum strain reached a critical level of that deformation case, the emergency indicator was activated. If the RMS values were over 0.001, the program showed that these cases were not in the database. When a case is not in the database, it is necessary to decide which of these deformations should be considered as new cases. If the deformations are deemed worth consideration, then these new cases should be included in the database.

From the above procedures, the performance of the proposed post-processing algorithm with the FEM/FBG hybrid method was verified. For real applications, simulated data must be exchanged for real tested strain data. During normal operations, this management program acquires strain data to monitor the carbody. In the case of accidental carbody deformation, this post-processing algorithm will ascertain the health of the carbody.

Figure 6. Completed post-processing program.

CONCLUSION

This study suggests a health management algorithm for composite train carbody using FBG strain sensors. In this process, the FEM/FBG hybrid method was devised to determine effective sensor locations and construct the post processing algorithm. Based on the constructed algorithm, the complete program was embodied in LabVIEW software. Finally, using the reproduced simulation strain data for various deformations, the usefulness of this algorithm was successfully verified.

In case of derailment, each carbody of a train will have a variety of deformations and strain levels. Thus, the application of this health management algorithm is quite useful

because it can monitor the overall integrity of the train by monitoring the health of each carbody. Moreover, this post-processing program can be easily applied to not only other composite structures such as aircrafts, ships and bridges, but also to other metallic structures. This system may be used to efficiently determine if it is appropriate to reuse a composite carbody after accidents. Adopting this health management program, maintenance and labor expenses can be reduced because inefficient NDEs are not required for trivial cases of deformation.

In conclusion, a health management algorithm for composite train carbody was suggested in this study, and the usefulness of the post-processing method was verified using the acquired FBG strain data.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Korea Railroad Research Institute, Korea, for financial support.

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